

UDC 519.6:517.972.55

T. F. MYKCHAILOVA¹, Y. A. MAKSYMENKOVA^{2*}¹Dep. «Applied Mathematics», Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies, Lazaryana St., 2, Dnipro, Ukraine, 49010, tel. +38 (056) 373 15 35, e-mail michaylovatf@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0003-4609-7744^{2*}Dep. «Applied Mathematics», Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies, Lazaryana St., 2, Dnipro, Ukraine, 49010, tel. +38 (056) 373 15 35, e-mail mcsimenkoffa@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0002-3949-9553**The Problem of Minimax Estimation of Functionals for Non-Stationary Diffusion Processes**

Purpose. To model the technological process of analysis of energy sources that use random interference, it is necessary to apply special methods from the theory of minimax estimation and optimal control. The article proposes a method for solving the problem of minimax estimation of functionalities for the systems with distributed parameters with incomplete data for the process of neutron diffusion in a nuclear reactor. **Methodology.** In practice, in the study of non-stationary controlled processes of functioning of different energy sources there are measurement errors. As a rule, the exact values of errors are unknown, and therefore the desired solution of the equations in partial derivatives describing these processes is determined ambiguously. Therefore, it is advisable to set the task of calculating such an optimal estimate, which would best approximate the unknown value, taking into account the known information about the measurement errors. The best estimate can be achieved by applying a minimax approach to estimating functionals from the solutions of the partial differential equations of parabolic type. **Findings.** For a mathematical model of the neutron diffusion process in a nuclear reactor, the proposed method allows solving the problem of minimax estimation of the functional determined during the solution of the system describing this process. Since in real conditions of reactor operation there are always random obstacles (both in the equation describing the process and the function observed), the method allows finding a minimax estimate of the functional. The problem is reduced to the problem of optimal control with a given quality functionality, which is successfully solved. **Originality.** Using the methods of minimax estimation and optimal control of systems with distributed parameters, the best a priori estimation of the quality functional of the minimax estimation problem for the mathematical model of neutron diffusion in a nuclear reactor is obtained. **Practical value.** The method of minimax estimation of functionalities for differential equations of parabolic type proposed in the article allows reducing the problem to the problem of optimal control of the systems with distributed parameters, which can be implemented in Maple package using known algorithms.

Keywords: minimax functionals estimation; neutron diffusion; optimal control theory; parabolic type problems

Introduction

Nowadays, the role of the theory of optimal control in solving various applied problems is constantly growing. Continuous complication of the energy systems, increasing their capacity, makes it important to apply the control theory to optimize such systems and their components. The systems powered by the nuclear power plants are of interest in this regard [2, 4, 9].

The theory of optimal control of systems with distributed parameters [3, 4] considers the processes of thermal conductivity and diffusion, which are used during the analysis of various energy sources [2, 7]. Improvements of various chemical reactors, as well as the chemical plants based on the use of atomic and thermal energy, make the problem of optimizing the thermal and diffusion processes, which are described

by differential and integro-differential equations in partial derivatives [6, 8]. One of the stages of research and optimal control of nonstationary neutron diffusion process in nuclear reactors is the problem of describing a mathematical model and estimating the functional determined during the solution of the system describing the process [2, 8]. Note that the solution of the control problem of the system with distributed parameters is complicated by the fact that in real conditions of the reactor operation random external interference, noise, occur naturally. In this case, the method of minimax functional estimation for parabolic equations is used. In [5, 6, 9], the algorithm of minimax estimation of functionals for the parabolic type equations is applied, which reduces the problem to the problem of optimal control with a given quality functional on the basis of the works.

Purpose

The main purpose of our study is to apply the method of minimax estimation of functionals for the parabolic type problem, which describes the process of the neutron diffusion in a nuclear reactor and construction of the best a priori estimation of the quality functional.

Methodology

In practice, measurement errors take place during the study of non-stationary controlled processes of functioning of different energy sources. As a rule, the exact values of errors are unknown, and therefore the desired solution of the equations in partial derivatives describing these processes is determined ambiguously. Therefore, it is advisable to set the task of calculating such an optimal estimate, which would best approximate the unknown value, taking into account the known information about the measurement errors. The best estimate can be achieved by applying a minimax approach to estimating the functionals from the solutions of the partial differential equations of parabolic type.

Findings

The nonstationary process of neutron diffusion in a nuclear reactor (taking into account the delayed neutrons of the first group) can be described by equation [1, 3]

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = D_0 \frac{\partial^2 N}{\partial x^2} + \frac{k_0 - 1}{T_0} N + \frac{k_1 \lambda_1}{T_0} \int_0^\infty N(x, t - \tau) e^{-\lambda_1 \tau} d\tau + f(x, t) \quad (1)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$N|_{x=-a} = 0; N(x, t) \in L_2[(-a, a), (0, \infty)] \quad (2)$$

and initial conditions:

$$N(x, 0) = N_0(x) + f_0(x), \quad (3)$$

where N – thermal neutrons density; k_0 – fast neutron multiplication factor; T_0 – thermal neutron lifetime; k_1 – multiplication factor of the delayed neutrons of the first group; $1/\lambda_1$ – lifetime of the delayed neutrons of the first group; D_0 – diffusion coefficient.

Let us observe the value

$$y(t_j) = y_j = \int_{-a}^a c(x) N(x, t_j) dx + \eta_j, \quad j = \overline{1, m} \quad (4)$$

where $c(x) \in L_2^m(-a, a)$ – is a known function.

As for the functions $f(x, t)$, $f_0(x)$ and $\eta(t)$, which are random interference, we assume that they belong to some area:

$$G = \left\{ f, \eta : \left| \int_{-a}^a f_0^2(x) dx + \int_0^T \int_{-a}^a f^2(x, t) dx dt + \sum_{j=1}^m \eta_j^2 \right| \leq 1 \right\}. \quad (5)$$

We should estimate the functional

$$I(N) = \int_{-a}^a l(x) N(x, T) dx, \quad (6)$$

where $l(x)$ – is a given piecewise continuous function.

We search for the estimation of the functional (6) in the form

$$\hat{I}(N) = - \sum_{j=1}^m U_j y_j. \quad (7)$$

We obtain the problem of finding the minimax estimate [4, 5]:

$$\min_{U_j} \sup_G |I(N) - \hat{I}(N)|^2. \quad (8)$$

Let us reduce the initial-boundary value problem for the integro-differential equation (1) to the initial-boundary value problem for the system of two differential equations. To do this, let us introduce the function

$$r_1(x, t) = \frac{k_1}{T} \int_0^\infty N(x, t - \tau) e^{-\lambda_1 \tau} d\tau, \quad (9)$$

that satisfies the equation

$$\frac{\partial r_1}{\partial t} = \frac{k_1}{T_0} N(x, t) - \lambda_1 r_1(x, t). \quad (10)$$

Then equation (1) becomes a system of differential equations

ІНФОРМАЦІЙНО-КОМУНІКАЦІЙНІ ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ ТА МАТЕМАТИЧНЕ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = D_0 \frac{\partial^2 N}{\partial x^2} + \frac{k_0 - 1}{T_0} N + \lambda_1 r_1(x, t) + f(x, t) \\ \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial t} = \frac{k_1}{T_0} N - \lambda_1 r_1(x, t); \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

with initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} N(x, 0) &= N_0(x) + f_0(x); \\ r_1(x, 0) &= \frac{k_1}{T_0 \lambda_1} (N_0(x) + f_0(x)). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Let us introduce the designations

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{k}^* &= \left[1, \frac{k_1}{T_0 \lambda_1} \right]; \\ \bar{f}^*(x, t) &= [f(x, t), 0]; \\ \bar{f}_0^*(x) &= \left[f_0(x), \frac{k_1}{T_0 \lambda_1} f_0(x) \right] = f_0(x) \bar{k}^*; \\ \bar{N}_0^*(x) &= \left[N_0(x), \frac{k_1}{T_0 \lambda_1} N_0(x) \right] = N_0(x) \bar{k}^*; \\ \bar{N}^*(x, t) &= [N(x, t), r_1(x, t)]; \\ \bar{D}_0 &= \begin{bmatrix} D_0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \\ B &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{k_0 - 1}{T_0} & \lambda_1 \\ \frac{k_1}{T_0} & -\lambda_1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Let us record (11) in vector form:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{N}}{\partial t} = \bar{D}_0 \frac{\partial^2 \bar{N}}{\partial x^2} + B \bar{N} + \bar{f}; \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{N}(x, 0) = \bar{k}^* (N_0(x) + f_0(x)); \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{N}(x, t)|_{-a}^a = 0 \quad (16)$$

We have the following theorem:

The problem of minimax estimate of the functional $\min_{U_j} \sup_G |I(N) - \hat{I}(N)|^2$ is equivalent to the

problem of optimal system management:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}}{\partial t} = -\bar{D}_0 \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\Psi}}{\partial x^2} - B^* \bar{\Psi} - c(x) \sum_{j=1}^m U_j \delta(t - t_j); \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, t)|_{-a}^a = 0; \quad (18)$$

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, T) = \bar{l}(x), \quad (19)$$

with a quality criterion

$$\begin{aligned} I(U_j) &= \left(\int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* N_0(x) \bar{\Psi}(x, 0) dx \right)^2 + \\ & \int_{-a}^a \left(\bar{k}^* \bar{\Psi}(x, 0) \right)^2 dx + \\ & \int_0^T \int_{-a}^a \bar{\Psi}^2(x, t) dx dt + \sum_{j=1}^m U_j^2, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $\bar{l}^* = [l(x), 0]$, $\bar{\Psi}(x, t) = [\psi_1(x, t), \psi_2(x, t)]$.

Let us replace the variables:

$$t' = T - t; \quad t = T - t'; \quad \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}}{\partial t'}. \quad (21)$$

If we omit ' in the variable t' , we obtain the following optimal control problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}}{\partial t} &= -\bar{D}_0 \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\Psi}}{\partial x^2} + B^* \bar{\Psi} + \\ & + c(x) \sum_{j=1}^m U_j \delta(T - t - t_j); \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, t)|_{-a}^a = 0; \quad (23)$$

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, 0) = \bar{l}(x). \quad (24)$$

It is necessary to minimize the function:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{U_j} I[U_j] &= \\ & = \min_{U_j} \left\{ \left(\int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* N_0(x) \bar{\Psi}(x, T) dx \right)^2 + \right. \\ & \left. \int_{-a}^a \left(\bar{k}^* \bar{\Psi}(x, T) \right)^2 dx + \int_0^T \int_{-a}^a \bar{\Psi}^2(x, t) dx dt + \sum_{j=1}^m U_j^2 \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

ІНФОРМАЦІЙНО-КОМУНІКАЦІЙНІ ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ ТА МАТЕМАТИЧНЕ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ

Let us solve the problem of optimal control.

We search the solution of problem (22) – (24) in the form of a Fourier series by eigenfunctions of the corresponding Sturm-Liouville problem:

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \bar{\Psi}_n(t) X_n(x);$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_n = \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_n \\ r_n \end{pmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

$$X''(x) + p^2 X(x) = 0;$$

$$X(a) = X(-a) = 0. \quad (26)$$

For Fourier coefficients, problem (22) – (24) is recorded as an infinite number of systems of two ordinary differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \bar{\Psi}_n}{\partial t} = \left(-D_0 \rho_n^2 + \frac{k_0 - 1}{T_0} \right) \Psi_n + \frac{k_1}{T_0} r_n(t) = \\ = C_n \sum_{j=1}^m U_j \delta_j(T - t - t_j); \\ \frac{\partial r_n}{\partial t} = \lambda_1 \Psi_n - \lambda_1 r_n. \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Let us denote the elements of the fundamental matrix of the problem (27) by $F_{kmi}(t), k, m = \overline{1, 2}$. They can be obtained in the closed form. Then the solution of the initial system (22) will have the following form:

$$\bar{\Psi}(x, t) = \int_{-a}^a F(x, y, t) \bar{l}(y) dy +$$

$$+ \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\int_{-a}^a F(x, y, t - (T - t_j)) \bar{l}(y) dy \right) U_j, \quad (28)$$

where $F(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} X_i(x) X_i(y) \Phi_i(t)$.

We substitute $\bar{\Psi}(x, t)$ into the functional $I[U]$, calculate the variation of this functional, using the necessary optimality conditions and obtain a system of equations

$$U_l + \sum_{j=1}^m A_{lj} U_j = D_l, l = \overline{1, m}, \quad (29)$$

where the matrix $[A_{lj}]$, the column of free terms D_l , the coefficients $\mu_1^l \mu_2^l(x)$ and $\mu_3^l(x, t)$ are calculated by formulas:

$$A_{lj} = \mu_1^l \int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* N_0(x) \int_{-a}^a F(x, y, t_j) \bar{c}(y) dy dx +$$

$$+ \int_{-a}^a \mu_2^l(x) \bar{k}^* \int_{-a}^a F(x, y, t_j) \bar{c}(y) dy dx +$$

$$+ \int_0^T \int_{-a}^a \mu_3^l(x, t) \int_{-a}^a F_{11}(x, y, T - t_j) c(y) dy dx dt;$$

$$D_l = -\mu_1^l \int_{-a}^a \int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* N_0(x) F(x, y, T) \bar{l}(y) dy dx -$$

$$- \int_{-a}^a \mu_2^l(x) \bar{k}^* \int_{-a}^a F(x, y, T) \bar{l}(y) dy dx -$$

$$- \int_0^T \int_{-a}^a \mu_3^l(x, t) \int_{-a}^a F_{11}(x, y, t) l(y) dy dx dt;$$

$$\mu_1^l = \int_{-a}^a \int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* N_0(x) F(x, y, t_l) \bar{c}(y) dy dx;$$

$$\mu_2^l(x) = \int_{-a}^a \bar{k}^* F(x, y, t_l) \bar{c}(y) dy;$$

$$\mu_3^l(x, t) = \int_{-a}^a F_{11}(x, y, t - (T - t_l)) \bar{c}(y) dy.$$

From the system (29) we determine the impulse controls $U_l = \sum_{j=1}^m G_{lj} D_j$, where $G_{lj} = [I + A_{lj}]^{-1}$.

We define functions $\bar{\Psi}(x, t)$ from (28). Having substituted the obtained values $\bar{\Psi}(x, t)$ and U_l in (25), we find the best a priori estimate of the functional (20).

The proposed method of minimax estimation can be implemented on a PC using the Maple system [1, 3, 10].

The given solution method of the problem of minimax estimation of functionalities for the systems with distributed parameters in case of incomplete data will allow investigating the nonstationary processes in modern energy systems using the theory of optimal control. Since in real conditions of reactor operation there are always random obstacles (both in the equation describing the process and the function observed), the method allows finding a minimum estimate of the functional. The problem

ІНФОРМАЦІЙНО-КОМУНІКАЦІЙНІ ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ ТА МАТЕМАТИЧНЕ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ

is reduced to the problem of optimal control with a given quality functionality, which can be successfully solved.

Originality and practical value

It is shown that using the methods of optimal control theory for parabolic problems it is possible to solve the problem of minimax estimation of functionalities for the systems with distributed parameters in case of incomplete data, which simulates the process of neutron diffusion in a nuclear reactor. The proposed methodology allows implementing the algorithm of direct finding the best a priori estimate of

the quality functional for the diffusion process in a nuclear reactor. For specific numerical data, this can be implemented in the Maple system.

Conclusions

This article describes the method of minimax estimation of functionalities in models of nonstationary diffusion processes in energy systems with incomplete data. In particular, the problem of minimax estimation of the functional can be solved using the methods of the optimal control theory.

LIST OF REFERENCE LINKS

1. Бабич Ю. А., Михайлова Т. Ф. Аппроксимация периодических функций многих переменных функциями меньшего числа переменных в метрических пространствах орлича. *Український математичний журнал*. 2018. Т. 70, № 8. С. 1143–1148.
2. Егоров А. И. *Оптимальное управление тепловыми и диффузионными процессами*. Москва : Наука, 1978. 464 с.
3. Егоров А. И. *Обыкновенные дифференциальные уравнения и система Maple*. Москва : СОЛОН-ПРЕСС, 2016. 392 с.
4. Наконечный А. Г., Акименко В. В., Трофимчук О. Ю. Модель оптимального управления системой интегро-дифференциальных уравнений с вырождающейся параболичностью. *Кибернетика и системный анализ*. 2007. № 6. С. 90–102.
5. Наконечный А. Г. *Минимаксное оценивание функционалов от решений вариационных уравнений в гильбертовых пространствах*. Киев : КГУ, 1985. 92 с.
6. Наконечный О. Г. *Оптимальне керування та оцінювання в рівняннях із частинними похідними*: навчальний посібник. Київ : Видавничо-поліграфічний центр «Київський університет», 2004. 103 с.
7. Galaktionov V. A, Svirshchevskii S. R. *Exact solutions and invariant subspaces of nonlinear partial differential equations in mechanics and physics*. Chapman and Hall/CRC Press, 2007. 528 p.
8. Kapustyan V. O., Pyshnograiev I. O. *Approximate Optimal Control for Parabolic–Hyperbolic Equations with Nonlocal Boundary Conditions and General Quadratic Quality Criterion*. *Advances in Dynamical Systems and Control*, 2016. P. 387–401. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40673-2_21
9. Kapustyan V. O., Pyshnograiev I. O. *Minimax Estimates for Solutions of parabolic-hyperbolic equations with Nonlocal Boundary Conditions*. *Continuous and Distributed Systems II*, 2015. pp. 277–296. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19075-4_17
10. Kogut, P. I., Maksimenkova, Yu. A. On regularity of weak solution to one class of initial-boundary value problem with pseudo-differential operators. *Journal of Optimization, Differential Equations, and Their Applications*. 2017. Vol. 25. Iss. 8. P. 70–108. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/141705>

Т. Ф. МИХАЙЛОВА¹, Ю. А. МАКСИМЕНКОВА^{2*}

¹Каф. «Прикладна математика», Український державний університет науки і технологій, вул. Лазаряна, 2, Дніпро, Україна, 49010, тел. +38 (056) 373 15 35, ел. пошта michaylovatf@ukr.net, ORCID 0000-0003-4609-7744

^{2*}Каф. «Прикладна математика», Український державний університет науки і технологій, вул. Лазаряна, 2, Дніпро, Україна, 49010, тел. +38 (056) 373 15 35, ел. пошта mcsimenkoffa@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0002-3949-9553

Задача мінімаксного оцінювання функціоналів для нестационарних процесів дифузії

Мета. Для моделювання технологічного процесу аналізу джерел енергії, що використовує випадкові перешкоди, необхідно застосувати спеціальні методи з теорії мінімаксного оцінювання та оптимального керування. У статті передбачено розробити методику розв'язання задачі мінімаксного оцінювання функціоналів для систем із розподіленими параметрами за неповних даних для процесу дифузії нейтронів у ядерному реакторі. **Методика.** На практиці під час дослідження нестационарних керованих процесів функціонування різних джерел енергії мають місце похибки вимірювань. Як правило, точні значення похибок невідомі, і тому шуканий розв'язок рівнянь у частинних похідних, що описують указані процеси, визначається неоднозначно. У зв'язку з цим доцільно ставити задачу обчислення такої оптимальної оцінки, яка найкращим чином наближала б невідому величину з урахуванням відомої інформації про похибки вимірів. Найкраща оцінка може бути досягнута за умови застосування мінімаксного підходу оцінювання функціоналів від розв'язків рівнянь із частинними похідними параболічного типу. **Результати.** Для математичної моделі процесу дифузії нейтронів у ядерному реакторі запропонована методика дозволяє розв'язати задачу мінімаксного оцінювання функціонала, визначеного під час розв'язку системи, що описує цей процес. Оскільки в реальних умовах функціонування реактора завжди наявні випадкові перешкоди (як у рівнянні, що описує процес, так і в функції, що спостерігається), методика дозволяє знайти мінімаксну оцінку функціонала. При цьому задача зводиться до задачі оптимального керування із заданим функціоналом якості, яку можна успішно розв'язати. **Наукова новизна.** За допомогою методів мінімаксного оцінювання та оптимального керування системами з розподіленими параметрами одержано найкращу апіорну оцінку функціонала якості для математичної моделі дифузії нейтронів у ядерному реакторі. **Практична значимість.** Запропонована в статті методика мінімаксного оцінювання функціоналів для диференціальних рівнянь параболічного типу дозволяє звести задачу до задачі оптимального керування системами з розподіленими параметрами, яка може бути реалізована в пакеті Maple з використанням відомих алгоритмів.

Ключові слова: мінімаксна оцінка функціоналів; дифузія нейтронів; теорія оптимального керування; задачі параболічного типу

REFERENCES

1. Babich, Y. A., & Michaylova, T. F. (2018). Approximation of Periodic Functions of Many Variables by functions of Smaller Number of Variables in Orlicz Metric Spaces. *Ukrains'kyi Matematychnyi Zhurnal*, 70(8), 1143-1148. (in Russian)
2. Yegorov, A. I. (1978). *Optimalnoe upravlenie teplovymi i diffuzionnymi protsessami*. Moscow: Nauka. (in Russian)
3. Yegorov, A. I. (2016). *Obyknovennyye differentsialnye uravneniya i sistema Maple*. Moscow: COLON-PPYeSS. (in Russian)
4. Nakonechniy, A. G., Akimenko, V. V., & Trofimchuk, O. Yu. (2007). Model optimalnogo upravleniya sistemoy integro-differentsialnykh uravneniy s vyrozhdaiushcheysoy parabolichnostyu. *Cybernetics and Systems Analysis*, 6, 90-102. (in Russian)
5. Nakonechnyy, A. G. (1985). *Minimaksnoe otsenivanie funktsionalov ot resheniy variatsionnykh uravneniy v gilbertovykh prostranstvakh*. Kyiv: KGU. (in Russian)
6. Nakonechnyy, O. G. (2004). *Optymaljne keruvannja ta ocinjuvannja v rivnjannjakh iz chastynnymy pokhidnymy: navchalnyj posibnyk*. Kyiv: Vydavnycho-polighrafichnyj centr «Kyjivsjkyj universytet». (in Ukrainian)
7. Galaktionov, V. A., & Svirshchevskii, S. R. (2007). *Exact solutions and invariant subspaces of nonlinear partial differential equations in mechanics and physics*. Chapman & Hall/CRC Press. (in English)
8. Kapustyan, V. O., & Pyshnograiev, I. O. (2016). *Approximate Optimal Control for Parabolic–Hyperbolic Equations with Nonlocal Boundary Conditions and General Quadratic Quality Criterion* (pp. 387-401). *Advances in Dynamical Systems and Control*. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40673-2_21 (in English)
9. Kapustyan, V. O., & Pyshnograiev, I. O. (2015). *Minimax Estimates for Solutions of parabolic-hyperbolic equations with Nonlocal Boundary Conditions* (pp. 277-296). *Continuous and Distributed Systems II*. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19075-4_17 (in English)

ІНФОРМАЦІЙНО-КОМУНІКАЦІЙНІ ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ ТА МАТЕМАТИЧНЕ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ

10. Kogut, P. I., & Maksimenkova, Yu. A. (2017). On regularity of weak solution to one class of initial-boundary value problem with pseudo-differential operators. *Journal of Optimization, Differential Equations, and Their Applications*, 25(8), 70-108. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/141705> (in English)

Received: August 13, 2021

Accepted: December 14, 2021